

This record provides an overview of the HEXA-X-II community on Zenodo, established in 2023. The community collects research outputs, reports, and other materials related to the HEXA-X-II project, which explores advanced wireless communication technologies and the evolution towards 6G. The purpose of this record is to offer a single, citable reference (via DOI) to the collection of SW/APIs and Datasets produced by project. For detailed materials, please refer to the individual records included in the community.

Keywords: 6G, wireless communication, HEXA-X-II, research community, datasets, publications

License: CC-BY-4.0

Creators: HEXA-X-II Consortium, Project contributors (see individual records for full author lists)

Category	Identifier	Open access record name and link to record or file	Licence	Link to version controlled source code (if available)
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.15125456	Designed API for the IBN-IME solution used in Hexa-X-II T2.3/T2.5 work	Apache License 2.0	
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14851978	MEC exposure and experience management API	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14752490	Trust Management API	GNU General Public License v3.0 or later	NA
Dataset	10.5281/zenodo.14616256	Hexa-X-II MLOps Failure Prediction Datasets	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14621433	akdd11/advancing-spectrum-anomaly-detection: v1.0	Apache License 2.0	GitHub - akdd11/advancing-spectrum-anomaly-detection: Code for the paper "Advancing Spectrum Anomaly Detection through Digital Twins", published in
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14283233	Sustainable MLOps Workflows Information Collector API	Apache License 2.0	
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14283028	Sustainable MLOps	Apache License 2.0	GitHub - Atos-Research-and-Innovation/HX-MLOps
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14193659	Multi-cluster extreme-edge resource orchestration API	Apache License 2.0	https://gitlab.com/resource-orchestration-and-automation/resource-automation-apis/-/blob/master/Multi-cluster%20extreme-
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14193635	Closed Loop Governance LCM API	Apache License 2.0	https://gitlab.com/resource-orchestration-and-automation/resource-automation-apis/-/blob/master/Closed%20Loop%20Governance%20LCM
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14193484	Closed Loop Governance - Catalogue API	Apache License 2.0	https://gitlab.com/resource-orchestration-and-automation/resource-automation-apis/-/blob/master/Closed%20Loop%20Governance%20-
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14192885	Monitoring jobs configuration	Apache License 2.0	https://gitlab.com/resource-orchestration-and-automation/resource-automation-apis/-/blob/master/Monitoring%20jobs%20configuration.json
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14191242	Level of Trust Assessment Function API	GNU General Public License v3.0 or later	GitHub - CyberDataLab/level-of-trust-framework: This repository contains the design and development of Level of Trust Assessment Function and Trust-based Intent
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14044742	TMF664 - Resource Function Activation and Configuration	Under copyright	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/tmforum-apis/TMF664_ResourceFunctionActivationConfiguration/refs/heads/master/TMF664-
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14044670	TMF640 - API Service Activation and Configuration	Under copyright	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/tmforum-apis/TMF640_ActivationConfiguration/refs/heads/master/TMF640-ServiceActivation-v4.0.0.swagger.json
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14032918	Conflict Detection for Control Loops Automation & Management API	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	
SW/API	10.5281/zenodo.14033410	DLT Service Federation API	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/hexa-x-ii/dlt-federation/-/blob/main/openapi.json https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/hexa-x-ii/dlt-
Dataset	10.5281/zenodo.7640353	Measurement-based MIMO channel model at 140GHz	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	